

ROLE OF EDUCATION IN SOCIO-CULTURAL DEVELOPMENT OF EGYPT

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Abstract. *Education is essential in the development and progression of every country. The level of education shows how developed the nation itself and the state itself as a whole are. This article revealed the importance of education and how important a role it plays in Egypt. The article also contains information from history, in particular about the reforms of Muhammad Ali, for the development of culture and education. In the 18th century, the role of the ulema in the history of the country increased. They began to actively penetrate the judicial system, thereby increasing their influence in society.*

Women's education and development is a top priority in Egypt. Over the past decades, the country has introduced a number of reforms to improve women's education. Women's education and measures for its development are also disclosed in this article.

Keywords: *education, social culture, globalization, Al-Azhar, Muhammad Ali's reforms, ulema, secondary and higher schools, women's education, "Supporting educational reform in Egypt."*

INTRODUCTION

Education is the most important factor in the development of the socio-cultural sphere of every society. It is education and the level of education that shows how developed a given society or state is. It has a direct impact on the dynamics of social and state progress. As noted in the scientific article by Oksana M.V., with the help of the education system as the main component of the institutional basis of society, scientific and humanitarian knowledge is disseminated, the foundation of the socio-cultural evolution of society is formed, in the creation of which the training of cultural, professional and highly qualified personnel acquires the main importance, able to create ideas and translate them into real life.

Education plays a very key role in the development of every state. This area is connected with all sectors of each state. It is also connected with all sectors of society: history, politics, culture, etc. Scientific sources claim that one of the main functions of this sphere as a socio-cultural institution is the formation of the human personality, the creation of which develops on the basis of certain and strictly selected moral principles and ethical standards. That is why, through educational processes, the level of citizens and society in society increases.

To develop the educational sector, each state, to one degree or another, invests its efforts in the form of cooperation, investment, financing, etc.

Education plays a very important role in achieving any goal. Education is considered an indicator not only of theoretical and practical knowledge, but also completely shapes and develops a person's worldview, and develops a person's personality. That is why the formation and development of education in universal human relations and values is considered the main task of every state and society.

In the 21st century, in the period of globalization and information technology, the development of education at the required level requires a lot of effort. The development of education is the development of the level of self-awareness of the people and the state as a whole.

This article reveals the role of education in the socio-cultural development of the Arab Republic of Egypt.

The emergence of the first centers of civilization and branches of education indicates that in Egypt quite a lot of attention is paid to the development of this area. It was from this period that the formation of the education sector began in Egypt. In the 18th century, Egypt was considered the center of traditional Muslim culture in the Arab world. It was during this period that the degree and level of education began to develop rapidly in Egypt. Cairo became the center where the first centers of education began to appear and form. madrasahs were gradually built here, where the most gifted, talented and intelligent people of that period gathered, in particular, ulemas, judges, teachers, teachers and imams. Al-Azhar University was formed at the mosque, which was considered the main cultural, educational and spiritual center, which for many years has been a branch of traditional ideology and training of the Muslim elite for society and the state. Historical sources note the following: primary education in the country was carried out by kuttabs - Koranic schools located in cities and regions of the country. They mainly carried out their activities at mausoleums or mosques and in other public places. In these kuttabas, minimal knowledge was obtained. Basically, Arabic was studied here for two or three years and the Koran was memorized. It was during this period that the role of the ulema strengthened. Their main merit is that the Egyptian ulema are beginning to actively penetrate the judicial system, which previously was practically hidden. Historical sources claim that if at the beginning, from the time of the Ottoman conquest, only Turks were appointed to judicial positions, and native Egyptians occupied only the position of naibs, then by the end of the 18th century. with rare exceptions, Egyptians themselves began to be appointed to judicial positions.

When it comes to the development of education, we need to note the era of Muhammad Ali. The contribution that Muhammad Ali made to the development of all spheres of society and the development of the state is considered very great. That is why the end of the 18th - beginning of the 19th centuries. It is commonly called the "golden age" in the history of Egypt. In 1805-1849. Significant changes occurred in the socio-economic and socio-cultural life of Egypt in connection with the reforms of Muhammad Ali. His main goal was to transform Egypt into a strong centralized state. A number of reforms were carried out on his part, including agrarian reform, the creation of a regular army and navy, the development of industry and agriculture, the development of education and culture. Muhammad Ali clearly understood that a strong army and navy were not enough to create a strong centralized state, so he paid special attention to the development of education, medicine and culture. Secular general education schools, as well as special schools in the field of medicine and technology, began to be built. A number of military schools were also built. A new education system was developed in the country, which differed from traditional religious education.

It was during this period that the number of students studying in schools and madrasahs increased significantly. For example, 2-3 thousand students studied at Al-Azhar University during this period.

The most important educational achievement of this period is that Muhammad Ali began sending dozens of young Egyptians to Europe to study Western languages, literature, law, military

science, and engineering. Special literature and textbooks in Western languages began to be translated into Arabic. The main priority of training in Europe was that the Egyptians trained there, upon returning to the country, became officials, worked as managers in government agencies, and the military immediately received the position of officer.

As noted above, under Muhammad Ali, schools with secular education appeared and civilian hospitals and military hospitals began to open. During training in military institutions, the state provided students with food, clothing, educational supplies, and also paid a certain stipend. The teachers were also French, Spanish, etc.

All these factors in the field of education played a very important role in the development and improvement of the level of socio-cultural life of society.

The movement for spiritual and cultural development, which began in the middle of the 20th century, was caused by the need to gain access to the achievements of modern technology and science. Gaining access meant creating a new society and a new state. The 1952 revolution is evidence of this. It was during this period that the restructuring and change of the education system in Egypt began. As noted in the sources, a course was taken to eliminate illiteracy, Arabize teaching, that is, develop education in Arabic, create terms in Arabic, and develop secondary specialized and higher education. The number of educational institutions has increased. Education became free and compulsory, enshrined in the Law of the country. Economic conditions in Egypt mainly required the creation of a functional system in the field of education, satisfying the need for highly qualified personnel who could in the future make a real contribution to overcoming economic backwardness and increasing the level of industrial production. Only with the help of a huge layer of technical intelligentsia and engineering workers is the country able to increase economic opportunities, develop industrial sectors, and achieve noticeable success in agriculture. According to statistics, Egypt has been developing autumn at a rapid pace in recent decades. In particular, in the field of economic industry and production, a high increase in progress has been observed, which in turn distinguishes Egypt from neighboring countries with notable achievements not only in the field of economy, but also in other areas of activity, including the educational sphere. Thanks to these achievements, Egypt ranks quite high in terms of the number of students in secondary and higher education among Arab countries. Based on scientific sources, it can be noted that the growth of the educational sector was noticed due to an increase in the infrastructure and functioning of education, improvement in the selection of personnel, processing and addition of training personnel and teaching methods.

When it comes to the progression of the education system, it is also necessary to note about women's education, which is of some importance in the socio-cultural life of society. Women's education has a special place in Egypt. An educated woman means educated children and an educated nation. Today, the country is creating all the conditions to increase female literacy, as it has a significant impact on the progress of society and all segments as a whole. Scientific sources note that the Egyptian government fully supports and invests in women's education, not only for economic growth, but also for the successful implementation of the family planning program and improving the health of children, since women's education brings significant benefits not only to themselves, but also to society.

At the present time, in the Arab Republic of Egypt, all possible conditions are being created to improve the system and sphere of education. The government has taken a number of laws, reforms and agreements to implement these conditions. Egypt is trying to strengthen its diplomatic

ties in the field of education with many countries and states. A striking example of this can also be the Uzbek-Egyptian friendly and mutually beneficial relations in the field of education. It is important to note that today, very strong relations have developed in this area between the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Arab Republic of Egypt, since Uzbekistan has been conducting its diplomatic mission with Egypt since 1992. In the educational field, a number of joint reforms have been carried out between the two countries. For example, in Uzbekistan, much attention is paid to the study of Arabic language, literature, hadith studies, etc. Today, in such higher educational institutions of Uzbekistan as the Tashkent State University of Oriental Studies, the International Islamic Academy, and the State University of World Languages, more than four thousand students study Arabic language and literature. These universities hold various events, holidays, and weeks in honor of this language. Also in Egypt, the number of Uzbek students is increasing. Especially recently, many Uzbek students have shown a great desire to study at the religious university Al-Azhar. Since Al-Azhar is considered one of the most famous and sought-after religious institutions of higher education in the world. All these indicators indicate strong friendly and diplomatic ties between the two republics. Also today, in connection with this project, a number of changes in education have been implemented. For example, new projects in education were developed, curricula were changed, and professional teachers from neighboring countries were invited. Thanks to these changes, the illiteracy rate among Egyptians has decreased markedly. In secondary schools and higher educational institutions, the percentage of pupils and students wishing to continue their education began to increase. Many Egyptian students have begun to study or continue their education abroad or in neighboring countries, such as Saudi Arabia, the UAE, Lebanon, as well as the UK and Washington. Students study abroad for a certain period of time and then return home to continue their teaching activities.

Every developing country pays great attention to the development of the education sector. Because thanks to education, you can achieve certain heights in many areas. The level of education greatly depends on the conditions created in a particular country. If the conditions are sufficient, then the level and indicator of education are also high.

To support all areas of society, in particular for the development of education and also women's education, in 2018 in Egypt, the Ministry of Education began implementing the project "Supporting Education Reform in Egypt." The main goals and objectives of this project are to increase literacy and the level of education among Egyptians.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion of this article, it is important to note that all these reforms indicate that education is considered a very important sphere of society and plays a huge role in the socio-cultural life of the Arab Republic of Egypt.

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